

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Oxovanadium(V) with Dipicolinic Acid and Some Monobasic Bidentate Nitrogen, Oxygen Donor Ligands

S. K. SENGUPTA*, S. K. SAHNI and R. N. KAPOOR

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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The reactions of oxovanadium(V) trichloride and oxovanadium(V) triethoxide with dipicolinic acid (primary ligand, dipicH_2) and several nitrogen, oxygen donor molecules (secondary ligand, N-OH) viz., picolinic acid, nicotinic acid, isonicotinic acid, glycine, aminophenol, *o*-aminobenzoic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid have been studied in anhydrous benzene. The reaction products isolated are of the types $[\text{VO}(\text{dipic})(\text{dipicH})]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{dipic})(\text{N-O})]$ and have been characterized by elemental analyses, magnetic moment and infrared spectral studies. The parent complex $[\text{VO}(\text{dipic})(\text{dipicH})]$ is found to have a seven coordinate, monomeric structure. A polymeric seven coordinate structure has been assigned for the mixed ligand complexes.

THE versatile chelating ability of dipicolinic acid with various metals is well established¹. Structural studies have shown that dipicolinic acid can form various types of complexes having different types of bonding, depending on the nature of the metal ion and reaction conditions²⁻⁶. The interest in such complexes continues to increase because of the possibility of their use as models to explain some intricate reactions in biological systems^{7,8}. However, very little work has been reported on the oxo-transition metal dipicolinates¹. Scattered data are available on oxovanadium(III) and oxovanadium(IV) complexes of dipicolinic acid^{9,10}, but no reference is available on the oxovanadium(V) complexes of these ligands though some oxovanadium(V) complexes of simple carboxylic acids have been studied^{11,12}. There is a difference of opinion over the solvolysis of vanadyl(V) chloride in carboxylic acids. Seifert isolated a brown complex, $[\text{VO}(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2]$, from the solvolysis of VOCl_3 in acetic acid¹¹. Recently, a yellow vanadium(V) complex, $[\text{VO}_2(\text{O}_2\text{CCH}_3)_2]$, has been reported¹². Further studies however could not be undertaken because of the readily hydrolysable nature of these complexes.

The present paper deals with the reactions of vanadyl(V) chloride (VOCl_3) and vanadyl(V) ethoxide $[\text{VO}(\text{OEt})_3]$ with dipicolinic acid (dipicH_2) and different secondary ligands, picolinic acid (picH), nicotinic acid (nicH), isonicotinic acid (glyH), aminophenol (apH), glycine (glyH), *o*-aminobenzoic acid (oabH) and *p*-aminobenzoic acid (pabH). The complexes have been isolated in solid state and characterized on the basis of spectral and magnetic data.

Experimental

The pyridine carboxylic acids, amino carboxylic acids and aminophenol, used as ligands in the preparation of mixed ligand complexes, were AnalaR grade (B.D.H. and E. Merck). VOCl_3 and $\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ were prepared by reported methods^{13,14}. All glass apparatus used were fitted with Quickfit interchangeable joints. Extreme precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Benzene was dried by literature procedure¹⁵.

Infrared spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Perkin Elmer-621 spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out by Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant. An Elico conductivity bridge, type CM 8 2T was used for conductance measurements at room temperature.

Vanadium was estimated as its pentoxide¹⁶ after decomposing the complex with concentrated nitric acid. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method and alcohols by an oxidimetric method¹⁷.

Reaction of vanadyl(V) chloride with dipicolinic acid: The parent complex of oxovanadium(IV) with dipicolinic acid, $[\text{VO}(\text{dipic})(\text{dipicH})]$, was synthesized by adding a dry benzene solution of dipicolinic acid to vanadyl(V) chloride in 2 : 1 molar ratio and refluxing the solution for 5 hr. The brown coloured mass thus obtained was filtered, thoroughly washed with benzene and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} .

Reactions of vanadyl(V) chloride with dipicolinic acid and some N, O donor molecules: Weighed amounts of dipicolinic acid and the appropriate secondary ligand were added to a dry round

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur-273 001.

bottomed flask (100 ml) containing weighed amount of vanadyl trichloride in dry benzene (50-60 ml) kept in ice cold water, in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was refluxed and evolution of hydrogen chloride started after 30 min with the formation of coloured precipitate. Refluxing was continued until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased (6-12 hr). Afterwards, the solution was cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The product was thoroughly washed with benzene and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} .

Reaction of vanadyl(V) ethoxide with dipicolinic acid: An weighed amount of dipicolinic acid was added to a dry flask containing an weighed amount of vanadyl triethoxide in dry benzene. The contents were refluxed and ethanol liberated was removed azeotropically with benzene (68-72°). The brown coloured precipitate was filtered, thoroughly washed with benzene and dried under vacuum.

Reactions of vanadyl(V) ethoxide with dipicolinic acid and some N, O donor molecules: To vanadyl(V) triethoxide (1.0 mole) in dry benzene (60 ml) was added dipicolinic acid (1.0 mole) and appropriate secondary ligand (1.0 mole). The mixture was refluxed and ethanol liberated was removed azeotropically with benzene (68-72°). A brown coloured precipitate began to appear only 10 min after the reaction had started. However, the reaction was continued until all liberated ethanol was fractionated out (10-18 hr). After the completion of the reaction, the excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the brown solid was thoroughly washed with benzene and dried.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Tables 1 and 2) reveal 1 : 2 metal to ligand stoichiometry for the parent metal-dipicH₂ complex and 1 : 1 : 1 (metal : dipicH₂ : N-O⁻) for the mixed ligand complexes, where

N-O⁻ represents a monobasic bidentate ligand viz., picolinic acid, nicotinic acid, isonicotinic acid, glycine, aminophenol, *o*-aminobenzoic acid or *p*-aminobenzoic acid. The stoichiometry of the complexes isolated during the reactions of VOCl₃ or VO(OEt)₃ is the same, confirming the replacement of all chlorine or all ethoxy groups from the starting material. The parent complex of dipicolinic acid is soluble in dimethylformamide, dimethylsulphoxide, nitrobenzene and partially in ethanol and acetone, whereas the mixed ligand complexes are partially soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. The electrical conductance of the mixed ligand complexes, measured in dimethylformamide shows them essentially to be non-electrolytes. All the complexes are sensitive to moisture.

The room temperature magnetic moment measurements, carried out in dry box, indicates the diamagnetic nature of all these complexes confirming the +5 oxidation state of oxovanadium.

Infrared spectra: The important infrared spectral bands are given in Table 3. The ir spectrum of dipicolinic acid shows two bands at 1700 and 1300 cm⁻¹, due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{COO}$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{COO}$ vibrations, respectively. In the mixed ligand complexes, these two bands appear at ca 1600-1580 and 1460-1430 cm⁻¹, respectively, indicating the involvement of carboxylic group in bond formation with metal¹⁸⁻²⁰. This is also supported by the appearance of new bands at ca 400-380 cm⁻¹, assignable²¹ to $\nu(\text{V}-\text{O})$ vibration. However, it is worth noting that the lowering (ca 100 cm⁻¹) of $\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{COO}$ (which is mainly due to >C=O of COOH group) and also the difference ($\Delta\nu = \nu_{\text{asym}}\text{COO} - \nu_{\text{sym}}\text{COO}$) of ~ 180-170 cm⁻¹ are considerable, which clearly indicate that the >C=O moiety of -COOH group is also coordinated to another metal atom, resulting in the observed lowering due to drainage of electrons

TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF OXOVANADIUM(V) TRICHLORIDE WITH DIPICOLINIC ACID AND DIFFERENT N, O DONOR LIGANDS

Reactants	Molar ratio	Refluxing time hr	Product isolated colour, yield %	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)	
				V	N
VOCl ₃ + dipicH ₂	1 : 2	5	VO(dipic)(dipicH) brown, 72	12.52 (12.86)	6.82 (7.07)
VOCl ₃ + dipicH ₂ + picH	1 : 1 : 1	8	VO(dipic)(pic) brown, 63	14.20 (14.39)	7.42 (7.91)
VOCl ₃ + dipicH ₂ + nicH	1 : 1 : 1	8	VO(dipic)(nic) brown, 60	13.95 (14.39)	7.52 (7.91)
VOCl ₃ + dipicH + inicH	1 : 1 : 1	8	VO(dipic)(inic) brown, 58	14.07 (14.39)	7.25 (7.91)
VOCl ₃ + dipicH + glyH	1 : 1 : 1	8	VO(dipic)(gly) brown, 65	16.26 (16.65)	8.79 (9.15)
VOCl ₃ + dipicH + apH	1 : 1 : 1	5	VO(dipic)(ap) brown, 60	14.30 (14.98)	7.97 (8.28)
VOCl ₃ + dipicH + cabH	1 : 1 : 1	8	VO(dipic)(cab) brown, 68	13.50 (13.84)	7.39 (7.60)
VOCl ₃ + dipicH + pabH	1 : 1 : 1	8	VO(dipic)(pab) brown, 65	13.56 (13.84)	7.18 (7.60)

dipicH₂ = dipicolinic acid, picH = picolinic acid, nicH = nicotinic acid, inicH = isonicotinic acid, glyH = glycine, apH = aminophenol, cabH = *o*-aminobenzoic acid, pabH = *p*-aminobenzoic acid.

TABLE 2—REACTIONS OF OXOVANADIUM(V) TRIETHOXIDE WITH DIPICOLINIC ACID AND DIFFERENT N, O DONOR LIGANDS

Amount of reactants taken			Refluxing time hr	Product isolated colour, yield %	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)	
					Azeotrope	V
VO(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃ (2.0 g ; 0.009 mole)	+ dipicH ₂ (3.30 g ; 0.018 mole)		24	VO(dipic)(dipicH)	1.32 (1.33)	12.80 (12.86)
VO(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃ (1.0 g ; 0.004 mole)	+ dipicH ₂ (0.8 g ; 0.004 mole)	+ picH (0.6 g ; 0.004 mole)	20	VO(dipic)(pic)	0.65 (0.65)	13.82 (14.39)
VO(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃ (1.0 g ; 0.004 mole)	+ dipicH ₂ (0.85 g ; 0.005 mole)	+ nicH (0.62 g ; 0.005 mole)	24	VO(dipic)(nic)	0.64 (0.66)	14.20 (14.39)
VO(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃ (1.8 g ; 0.008 mole)	+ dipicH ₂ (1.85 g ; 0.008 mole)	+ inicH (1.0 g ; 0.009 mole)	24	VO(dipic)(inic)	1.18 (1.20)	14.08 (14.39)
VO(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃ (1.08 g ; 0.005 mole)	+ dipicH ₂ (0.8 g ; 0.005 mole)	+ glyH (0.045 g ; 0.006 mole)	35	VO(dipic)(gly)	0.73 (0.73)	16.20 (16.65)
VO(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃ (1.55 g ; 0.007 mole)	+ dipicH ₂ (1.2 g ; 0.007 mole)	+ aph (0.8 g ; 0.007 mole)	30	VO(dipic)(ap)	1.02 (1.05)	14.62 (14.98)
VO(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃ (1.0 g ; 0.004 mole)	+ dipicH ₂ (0.8 g ; 0.004 mole)	+ oabH (0.65 g ; 0.004 mole)	28	VO(dipic)(oab)	0.63 (0.66)	13.26 (13.85)
VO(OC ₂ H ₅) ₃ (1.0 g ; 0.004 mole)	+ dipicH ₂ (0.8 g ; 0.004 mole)	+ pabH (0.62 g ; 0.004 mole)	25	VO(dipic)(pab)	0.63 (0.66)	13.22 (13.84)

 TABLE 3—CHARACTERISTIC INFRARED BANDS (cm⁻¹)

Compound	$\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{COO}$	8a	$\nu_{\text{sym}}\text{COO}$	6a	16b	$\nu\text{V}-\text{O}$	$\nu\text{V}-\text{N}$	$\nu\text{V}-\text{py}$
VO(dipic)(dipicH)	1660 s	1620 m	1530 m	630 s	440 m	400 s	—	290 w
VO(dipic)(pic)	1670 s 1580 s	1615 m	1450 m	625 s	500 m	410 s	—	290 w
VO(dipic)(nic)	1665 m 1600 s	1615 m 1595 m	1460 m	620 s	480 m	400 s	—	280 w
VO(dipic)(inic)	1665 m 1610 s	1615 m	1455 m	635 s	495 m	380 s	—	—
VO(dipic)(gly)	1680 m 1600 s	1610 m	1440 m	630 s	440 m	400 s	380 w	280 w
VO(dipic)(ap)	1600 s	1615 m	1430 m	630 s	440 m	470 m 400 s	370 m	—
VO(dipic)(oab)	1665 w 1600 s	1610 m	1450 m	650 s	440 m	380 m	385 m	290 w
VO(dipic)(pab)	1670 m 1600 s	1615 m	1460 m	650 s	440 m	385 m	360 m	290 w

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak.

on coordination^{22,23}. This situation (I) is similar to the one observed by Nakamoto *et al*²⁴ in [Cu₂(OAc)₄].2H₂O (II) and later explained by Lever *et al*²⁵. However, in the parent dipicolinic acid complex, the shifting in $\nu_{\text{asym}}\text{COO}$ band is of the

order of 40-30 cm⁻¹ thereby excluding the possibility of coordination of the >C=O group to other metal atom²⁶. In different pyridine or amino carboxylic acids, these two bands appear at 1710-1690 and 1340-1320 cm⁻¹. On complexation, these bands also show similar type of changes as in parent dipicolinic acid complex, indicating the carboxylic

group coordination to vanadium atom^{27,28}. In the spectra of all the mixed ligand complexes, no band was observed in the region 3600-3200 cm⁻¹, indicating the complete absence of OH stretching vibration. A strong band due to $\delta(\text{OH})$ appearing at ~935 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the free carboxylic acids, was also found missing in the spectra of the above derivatives. However, in the parent dipicolinic acid complex, the OH group vibrations at 3200 cm⁻¹ (νOH) and 930 cm⁻¹ (δOH) persist. This fact indicates that in the parent complex, dipicolinic acid coordinates in deprotonated as well as in non-deprotonated forms in the same molecule of the complex. This type of bonding behaviour of dipicolinic acid has recently been shown in some lanthanide complexes^{28,29}.

The infrared spectra of *m*-aminophenol shows one band at 3350 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned³⁰ to νOH . However, this band disappears in its mixed ligand complex, indicating the bond formation of phenolic oxygen to metal through deprotonation. In the mixed ligand complexes of amino acids and

aminophenol the shifting of the ν_{NH} band appearing at ca 3300-3100 cm^{-1} in the ligands to lower frequency ($\sim 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicates the amino group coordination to vanadium atom³⁰. This has been confirmed by the appearance of new band at 380-360 cm^{-1} assignable²¹ to $\nu(\text{V}-\text{N})$.

The ligands containing the pyridine ring show bands at ca 1610-1570, 630-590 and 430-490 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned³¹ to 8a or 8b (ring deformation), 6a (an in-plane deformation) and 16b (out-of-plane deformation) vibrations, respectively. In the complexes, these bands show upward shift ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and in some cases the splitting of 6a band is also observed. The upward shift and splitting of 6a band are consistent with the pyridine nitrogen coordination to metal atom^{32,33}. The bands due to $\nu(\text{V}-\text{py})$ are located at 290-270 cm^{-1} . In all these complexes, the $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ vibration is found at 970-950 cm^{-1} .

Thus, on the basis of the above spectral features the above structures may tentatively be assigned for the parent (I) and the mixed ligand (II) complexes of oxovanadium (V). $\widehat{\text{N}}\text{O}$ represents different mononegatively charged secondary ligands viz., picolinic acid, nicotinic acid, isonicotinic acid, glycine, aminophenol, *o*-aminobenzoic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid.

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